

The Significant Related Party Transaction with Government Entities PRC's Listed State-owned Banks Failed to Disclose

1. PRC's Listed State-owned Banks are banks, who are controlled or mostly owned by the State Council of the People's Republic of China (PRC) by virtue of shareholdings or other means, that issue shares or debts publicly either in China or overseas. The banks hereafter to be discussed have securities traded overseas referred to in the paragraph 21 of Chinese Public Companies Systematically Omitted Disclosure of Related Party Transaction with Government-related Entities (Omission of Disclosure of Related Party Transaction by PRC's Listed State-owned Banks).¹ Securities of China Development Bank have also been issued overseas.

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Q china development bank		
1062	China Development Bank International Investment Ltd.	Equities
1606	China Development Bank Financial Leasing Co., Ltd. - H Shs	Equities
5020	China Development Bank 0.375% Notes 2021	Debt Securities
5021	China Development Bank 2.75% Notes 2022	Debt Securities
5080	China Development Bank 3.00% Notes 2022	Debt Securities
5355	China Development Bank 2.625% Notes 2022	Debt Securities
5356	China Development Bank 3.375% Notes 2027	Debt Securities
5357	China Development Bank 4.00% Notes 2037	Debt Securities
5359	China Development Bank 0.875% Notes 2024	Debt Securities
5388	China Development Bank HK Branch Floating Rate Notes 2022	Debt Securities

¹ These banks' securities are listed in Hong Kong and London. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5237202>

4 results (4 showing)

Issuer

Bonds

CHINA DEVELOPMENT BANK

77WQ CHINA DEVELOPMENT BANK 1.25% NTS 21/01/2023

Instruments: 2 | Amount raised: £1,000,000,000.00

Bonds

CHINA DEVELOPMENT BANK CORPORATION HONG KONG BRANCH

55GN CHINA DEV BANK CORP HONG KONG 1.875% NTS 03/11/2021

Instrument: 1 | Amount raised: £350,000,000.00

Bonds

CHINA DEVELOPMENT BANK HONG KONG BRANCH

46LQ CHINA DEV BANK HONG KONG BRANCH 0.375% NTS 24/01/2022

Instrument: 1 | Amount raised: £500,000,000.00

Bonds

AGRICULTURAL DEVELOPMENT BANK OF CHINA

16PG AGRICULTURAL DEVELOPMENT BANK OF CH 3.80% BDS 27/10/30

Instruments: 8 | Amount raised: £2,000,000,000.00

(Figure 1 Securities of China Development Bank)

2. It was also mentioned in the Omission of Related Party Transaction by PRC's Listed State-owned Banks that China State Construction Engineering

Corporation Ltd(中国建筑股份有限公司 or CSCEC) had been granted credit facility by PRC's Listed State-owned Banks as follows by 30 September 2019.

Currency Unit: RMB in billions

Bank name	Bank of China (中国银行)	China Construction Bank (中国建设银行)	Industrial and Commercial Bank of China (中国工商银行)	Bank of Communications Limited (交通银行)	Agricultural Bank of China (中国农业银行)	CDB (国家开发银行)
Credit facility	350	320	140	230	300	150
Used credit	95	200	80	70	130	120

截至2019年9月30日,中建股份及子企业在各银行的集团授信额度总计为2.1万亿元,已使用额度0.9万亿元,占授信总额的42.86%,主要授信情况如下表所示:

表 7-2: 发行人主要银行集团授信情况表

单位: 亿元

序号	授信银行	授信额度	已使用	未使用
1	中国建设银行	3200	2000	1200
2	中国银行	3500	950	2550
3	中国工商银行	1400	800	600
4	中国农业银行	3000	1300	1700
5	国家开发银行	1500	1200	300
6	中国进出口银行	400	90	310
7	交通银行	2300	700	1600
8	招商银行	700	220	480

(Figure 2 Credit Granted to CSCEC group by PRC's Listed State-owned Banks)

3. Other PRC's state-owned enterprises have also disclosed significant credit facility transaction with the banks in their legal documents but the banks also as usual failed to disclose them as related party transaction.

3.1 China National Petroleum Corporation (中国石油天然气集团有限公司 or CNPC), a state-owned enterprise, disclosed credit facility and borrowings from PRC's Listed State-owned Banks as of 30 September 2019 in a legal document as follows:

Currency Unit: RMB in billions

Bank name	BOC (中国银行)	CCB (中国建设银行)	ICBC (中国工商银行)	BOCOM (交通银行)	ABC (中国农业银行)
Credit facility	60	30	86	30	180
Used credit	19.12	8.83	50.49	-	60.34

截至 2019 年 9 月 30 日，发行人与中国工商银行股份有限公司、中国建设银行股份有限公司、中国农业银行股份有限公司、渣打银行、法国兴业银行等银行均有授信合作。发行人主要合作的五家国内银行授信额度合计 3,860.00 亿元，已使用 1,388.00 亿元，剩余授信额度 2,472.00 亿元。

表 7—1 发行人主要合作的国内银行授信情况

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单位：万元

序号	授信行	授信额度	已使用额度	未使用额度
1	中国银行	6,000,000	1,912,973	4,087,027
2	工商银行	8,600,000	5,049,186	3,550,814
3	建设银行	3,000,000	883,161	2,116,839
4	农业银行	18,000,000	6,034,636	11,965,364
5	交通银行	3,000,000	0	3,000,000
	合计	38,600,000	13,879,956	24,720,044

三、发行人控股股东与实际控制人

发行人为国有独资企业，现注册资本为48,690,000万元，根据国务院办公厅《关于公布国务院国有资产监督管理委员会履行出资人职责企业名单的通知》（国办发[2003]88号），由国资委履行出资人职责。发行人实际控制人和最终控制人为国务院国有资产监督管理委员会。

截至本募集说明书出具之日，发行人实际控制人持有发行人股份不存在任何质押或其他有争议的情况。

(Figure 3 CNPC group’s Credit Transaction with State banks)

3.2 China Railway Group Limited (中国中铁股份有限公司 or CRGL), a state-owned enterprise, disclosed credit facility and borrowings from PRC’s Listed State-owned Banks as of 30 September 2019 in a legal document as follows:

Currency Unit: RMB in billions

Bank name	BOC	CCB	ICBC (中国工商银行)	BOCOM (交通银行)	ABC	CDB
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	(中国银行)	(中国建设银行)			(中国农业银行)	(国家开发银行)
Credit facility	280	271.8	117.6	72.64	179	10.43
Used credit	122.87	215.3	77.41	57.76	61.7	0.6

截至2019年9月30日，公司及子公司获得各银行授信额度共计人民币133,090,622万元，其中尚未使用67,671,109万元。

表 9-1 发行人主要银行授信以及使用情况

单位：万元

序号	银行名称	集团授信情况		
		授信额度	已使用	未使用
1	中国工商银行北京西客站支行	11,760,187.13	7,741,179.23	4,019,007.90
2	中国农业银行总行营业部	17,900,000.00	6,170,000.00	11,730,000.00
3	中国银行总行营业部	28,000,000.00	12,287,000.00	15,713,000.00
4	中国建设银行总行营业部	27,180,000.00	21,530,000.00	5,650,000.00
5	北京银行	2,743,400.00	536,195.44	2,207,204.56
6	交通银行北京分行营业部	7,263,725.99	5,775,600.28	1,488,125.71
14	国开	1,043,262.00	59,579.00	983,683.00

三、发行人控股股东及实际控制人

(一) 发行人控股股东情况

公司的控股股东是中国铁路工程集团有限公司（简称“中铁工”）。截至募集说明书签署日，中铁工持有公司47.21%的股份。中铁工是由国务院国资委全资设立的，注册资本1,210,000.00万元，法定代表人张宗言。

(二) 发行人实际控制人情况

公司的实际控制人为国务院国有资产监督管理委员会，为国务院直属正部级特设机构，根据第十届全国人民代表大会第一次会议批准的国务院机构改革方案和《国务院关于机构设置的通知》设置。国务院授权国务院国资委代表国家履行出资人职责。国务院国资委的监管范围是中央所属企业（不含金融类企业）的国有资产。

(Figure 4 CRGL group's Credit Transaction with State banks)

3.3 China Communications Construction Company Ltd. (中国交通建设股份有限公司 or CCCCL) 's Credit Transaction with State banks as of 30 September 2019

Currency Unit: RMB in billions

Bank name	BOC (中国银行)	CCB (中国建设银行)	BOCOM (交通银行)	ABC (中国农业银行)	CDB (国家开发银行)
Credit facility	324.35	198.1	88.5	271.59	375.68
Used credit	127.8	134.02	58.02	122.85	291.4

目前，公司与国内多家银行保持良好的长期合作关系，并签署了综合授信协议。截至2019年9月30日，本公司拥有国内金融机构共19,858.34亿元的总授信额度，其中已使用授信额度约为10,028.79亿元，占授信总额50.50%，尚未使用的信贷额度为人民币9,829.55亿元。主要银行的授信情况如下：

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表 8-2 公司 2019 年 9 月 30 日主要银行授信情况

单位：亿元

序号	授信银行	授信额度	授信占用
1	中国银行股份有限公司	3,243.5	1,278
2	中国农业银行股份有限公司	2,715.86	1,228.52
3	中国建设银行股份有限公司	1,981	1,340.24
4	国家开发银行	3,756.82	2,914
5	交通银行股份有限公司	885	580.21

公司控股股东为中交集团,公司实际控制人为国务院国资委。股权关系如下:

图 5-3 公司股权关系图 (截至 2019 年 9 月 30 日)

截至 2019 年 9 月 30 日,中交集团合计持有本公司股份 9,447,440,2044 股,占公司总股本的 58.40% (其中中交集团直接持有公司股份 7,415,205,524 股,占公司总股本的 45.84%;通过发行可交换债开立的“中国交通建设集团有限公司—非公开发行 2017 年可交换公司债券质押专户”持有公司股份 2,032,234,680 股,占公司总股本的 12.56%)。

(Figure 5 CCCCL group’s Credit Transaction with State banks)

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4. According to the data in the paragraphs 2 and 3, the credit facility granted to four PRC state-owned entity groups by BOC was the most more than RMB1 trillion and credit used most more than RMB0.4 trillion was that granted by CCB (not including other state-owned entities that aren’t taken into consideration in this article, same for the other paragraphs).

Currency Unit: RMB in billions

Credit Facility:

Borrower Name	BOC(中国银行)	CCB (中国建设银行)	ICBC(中国工商银行)	BOCOM(交通银行)	ABC(中国农业银行)	CDB(国家开发银行)
CSCEC group	350	320	140	230	300	150

Borrower Name	BOC(中国银行)	CCB (中国建设银行)	ICBC(中国工商银行)	BOCOM(交通银行)	ABC(中国农业银行)	CDB(国家开发银行)
CNPC group	60	30	86	30	180	-
CRGLgroup	280	271.8	117.6	72.64	179	10.43
CCCCL group	324.35	198.1	-	88.5	271.59	375.68
Total	1,014.35	819.9	343.6	421.14	930.59	536.11

Credit Used:

Borrower Name	BOC(中国银行)	CCB (中国建设银行)	ICBC(中国工商银行)	BOCOM(交通银行)	ABC(中国农业银行)	CDB(国家开发银行)
CSCEC group	95	200	80	70	130	120
CNPC group	19.12	8.83	50.49		60.34	
CRGLgroup	122.87	215.3	77.41	57.76	61.7	0.6
CCCCL group	127.8	134.02		58.02	122.85	291.4
Total	236.99	424.13	207.9	127.76	252.04	120.6

(Figure 6 Overall Credit Transaction with State banks)

5. According to Consolidated Statements of Financial Position as of 31 December 2019, there were total equity of RMB1.98 trillion for BOC, RMB2.24 trillion for CCB, RMB2.69 trillion for ICBC, RMB0.8 trillion for BOCOM, RMB1.96 trillion for ABC and RMB1.39 trillion for CDB.

6. Take total equity as indicator of significance. The omission of related party transaction of both credit facility and credit used is significant.

Currency Unit: RMB in billions

Bank Name	BOC (中国银行)	CCB (中国建设银行)	ICBC (中国工商银行)	BOCOM (交通银行)	ABC (中国农业银行)	CDB (国家开发银行)	Total
Total Equity of Bank group	1,976.70	2,235.13	2,692.00	800.91	1,959.76	1,370.18	11,034.68
Credit Facility to four state-owned groups	1,014.35	819.9	343.6	421.14	930.59	536.11	4,065.69
Ratio	51.32%	36.68%	12.76%	52.58%	47.48%	39.13%	36.84%

Bank Name	BOC (中国 银行)	CCB (中国 建设银行)	ICBC (中国工 商银行)	BOCOM (交通银 行)	ABC (中 国农业银 行)	CDB (国家 开发银行)	Total
Credit Used by four state- owned groups	236.99	424.13	207.9	127.76	252.04	120.6	1,369.42
Ratio	11.99%	18.98%	7.72%	15.95%	12.86%	8.80%	12.41%

(Figure 7 Significance of Misstatement)